

ENHANCED INSIGHTS INTO TEMPORAL AND SEASONAL FLUCTUATIONS OF ARSENIC IN GROUNDWATER: INCORPORATING HYDROCHEMICAL ANALYSIS FOR SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF POLLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Arsenic contamination in groundwater presents a significant global threat to both human health and ecosystems. This element, occurring naturally, exhibits spatial and temporal dynamics influenced by geological, hydrological, and anthropogenic factors. Understanding these variations is crucial for developing effective mitigation strategies. In this study, we explore the hydrochemistry of arsenic and the contamination processes in the groundwater of the Ganga Brahmaputra river basin in India. Arsenic primarily exists in two oxidation states: arsenate (As^{5+}) and arsenite (As^{3+}), which can interconvert through oxidation of As^{3+} to As^{5+} and reduction of As^{5+} to As^{3+} . Additionally, arsenic can exist in organic forms resulting from biomethylation. Our investigation reveals clear temporal and seasonal variability in arsenic concentrations among water samples from Ballia and Ghazipur districts in eastern Uttar Pradesh (U.P.). During the post-monsoon season, arsenic concentrations decrease in samples, reflecting a relationship with rainfall intensity. Higher rainfall leads to increased dilution, lowering arsenic concentrations in groundwater during the monsoon period. Seasonal variations in groundwater flow dynamics are influenced by water level fluctuations and subsurface redox potential, particularly during heavy rainfall. Monsoon conditions contribute to rising groundwater levels due to shallow basin characteristics and flooding, resulting in reduced groundwater flushing rates. The study also explores advanced hydrochemical analysis techniques, such as isotopic tracing, speciation studies, and high-resolution monitoring approaches.

Keywords: Hydrochemistry of Arsenic, Temporal and Seasonal Variability, Pre- and Post-Monsoon, Arseneous Acid, Ganga Brahmaputra River

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INTRODUCTION

Arsenic, the 20th most abundant element naturally occurring in the Earth's crust, is widespread in soil and groundwater due to diverse sources, including industrial activities and natural processes like rock weathering, volcanic eruptions, and particle transportation through water or air [1]. This element's introduction into the atmosphere facilitates its circulation throughout the ecosystem.

In groundwater, arsenic primarily occurs in two oxidation states: arsenate (As^{5+}) and arsenite (As^{3+}), which can convert through oxidation of As^{3+} to As^{5+} and reduction of As^{5+} to As^{3+} . Arsenic also adopts an organic form via biomethylation, a process observed in living organisms such as plants, aquatic animals, and the human body, containing organoarsenic compounds. Microorganisms lacking chlorophyll undergo biomethylation, converting inorganic arsenic into organic forms [2,3].

Historically, high arsenic concentrations were localized to sulphide ores and metal oxides like iron oxide. Previous studies identified arsenic-contaminated groundwater mainly in the Ganga basin, originating from sulphide-rich mineralized areas in Bihar and surrounding basins. Recent research has detected elevated arsenic levels extending from the Indo-Gangetic alluvium westward to the Brahmaputra alluvium. During Holocene sediment deposition, hydroxides precipitate, capturing arsenic released during sulphide mineral weathering. Subsequent redox processes dissolve iron oxides, releasing arsenic into aquifers through biogeochemical pathways. Arsenic transported in the aqueous phase within the Ganga-Brahmaputra river basin is primarily found in sediments deposited during the late Quaternary and Holocene ages. Currently, arsenic-contaminated water results from arsenic mobilization via diverse biogeochemical processes [4,5,6,7,8].

Temporal and Seasonal Variability of Arsenic in Groundwater

Arsenic concentrations in groundwater exhibit pronounced temporal and seasonal variations across various samples, notably decreasing during the post-monsoon season. This variability is likely influenced by seasonal fluctuations in groundwater recharge and irrigation drawdown. MacArthur et al. observed a disparity in arsenic concentrations between pre and post-monsoon seasons, directly correlating with concentration levels. Farooq et al. (2010) highlighted a discernible association between arsenic behavior and rainfall intensity, with increased rainfall leading to higher dilution rates and reduced arsenic concentrations. The monsoon period experiences a significant decrease in arsenic concentration, reflecting the correlation between rainfall, dilution effects, and arsenic levels. Conversely, the winter season and pre-monsoon periods show increased arsenic concentrations due to reduced dilution effects [9,10,11].

The Oxidation of Arsenic-Rich Sulfide Minerals is common in geological deposits containing sulfide minerals with high arsenic content such as arsenopyrite (FeAsS), realgar (As₄S₄), and orpiment (As₂S₃). These minerals remain stable at significant depths beneath the Earth's surface but oxidize upon exposure to atmospheric conditions through natural weathering or mining activities. Arsenopyrite undergoes oxidative degradation upon contact with molecular oxygen (O₂) and water (H₂O), transforming arsenic into highly water-soluble arsenate (AsO₄³⁻). This process is particularly notable in bedrock aquifers experiencing oxidizing conditions during dry seasons, leading to a decrease in groundwater levels. The resulting release of Fe²⁺ into groundwater and oxidation of sulfur in sulfide minerals produces soluble SO₄²⁻ ions, which can leach into surrounding soil, groundwater, and surface water. Studies indicate that fluvial silt within the Ganga, Brahmaputra, and Meghna river systems primarily contains these sulfide minerals sourced from metamorphic and granitic Himalayan parent rocks. The presence of reduced levels of SO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ ions, along with their limited correlation with arsenic, suggests significant impacts of redox processes on arsenic mobilization [12,13,14,15,16,17].

Scorolite [FeAs₄, 2H₂O] and arsenopyrite originating from iron arsenite FeAsO₄ serve as significant sources of arsenic in groundwater. The coexistence of arsenic in oxidation states (As³⁺ and As⁵⁺) results in ferric arsenite and ferric arsenate. Under conditions of low pH and high Eh, ferric arsenate hydrolyzes into arsenic acid (H₃AsO₄) and ferric hydroxide, while ferric arsenite hydrolyzes into arsenious acid (H₃AsO₃) and ferric hydroxide.

In an acidic environment, Fe(OH)₃ is soluble; however, as acidity decreases, it undergoes precipitation. Both As³⁺ and As⁵⁺ ions adsorb onto the surface of the precipitated Fe(OH)₃ colloidal particles. The differential solubility of As³⁺ and As⁵⁺ ions leads to greater solubility of As⁵⁺ compared to As³⁺ ions. Therefore, the As³⁺ ion concentration in water surpasses that of As⁵⁺ ion. The pertinent chemical reactions are as follows:

1. $\text{FeAs}^{3+}\text{O}_4 + (2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}) \rightarrow \text{HAsO}_4^{2-} + \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$
2. $\text{FeAs}^{3+}\text{O}_3 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{As}^{3+}\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$

Under mild alkaline conditions, FeAs⁵⁺O₄ undergoes hydrolysis, resulting in the formation of Arsenic acid (H₃AsO₄) and Ferric hydroxide. In the biomethylation process, sediments initially undergo hydrolysis, producing Arsenic acid (H₃AsO₄), which is then reduced to arsenite (As³⁺O(OH)) by bacteria. This biomethylation process contributes to an increase in toxic arsenic concentrations. Bacteria further methylate arsenite into various soluble and highly toxic compounds, including methyl Arsenic acid (CH₃As⁵⁺O(OH)₂), dimethyl arsenic acid or cacodylic acid ((CH₃)₂As⁵⁺O(OH)), and trimethyl arsine ((CH₃)₃As³⁺). During agricultural activities, groundwater containing arsenic is extracted and subsequently absorbed by plants, animals, and humans from surface soil and water. Consequently, arsenic concentrations rise in both soil and water.

ARSENIC DISTRIBUTION IN BALLIA DISTRICT

In Ballia District, the distribution of arsenic in groundwater is intricately linked to the hydrological dynamics influenced by seasonal rainfall patterns. During the monsoon seasons, the groundwater level in Ballia experiences a substantial rise due to its low-lying shallow basin and flooding conditions, further elevating the groundwater level. As a result, the land remains waterlogged for a significant duration of the year, leading to lower rates of groundwater flushing. These conditions contribute to variations in the mean concentrations of arsenic observed during the monsoon season compared to the pre-monsoon season.

Table 1.1 Distribution of Arsenic during Post monsoon& Pre monsoon in Blocks of Ballia district

Blocks in Ballia district	As in ppb	
	Post monsoon	Pre monsoon
Belhari	542	731
Bansdeeh	545	690
Sikandarpur	129	180

During the investigation period, a significant correlation was observed between sedimentary rocks and water, facilitated by prolonged contact under slow-flowing water currents and conducive reducing conditions. This phenomenon contributed to elevated concentrations of arsenic (As) in groundwater. In the monsoon season, arsenic infiltrates the groundwater through the disintegration of Fe(III)-oxyhydroxides, whereas in the pre-monsoon period, arsenic adsorbs reversibly onto Fe(III)-oxyhydroxides. These dual processes exert control over arsenic concentrations in groundwater during the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon periods. Sampling sites in Ballia district, particularly Belhari, Bansdeeh, and Sikandarpur, were selected for detailed analysis [18,19].

ARSENIC DISTRIBUTION IN GHAZIPUR DISTRICT

In comparison, arsenic concentrations were found to be lower in the groundwater of Ghazipur district as opposed to Ballia district [20]. The spatial distribution of Oxidation-Reduction Potential (ORP) in groundwater indicated predominantly lower values in most wells. Elemental concentration variations were predominantly influenced by clay content in both the marginal and central areas. The sediments exhibited a progressive increase in finer particles and trace elements towards the central region, attributed to decreasing grain size. The concentration of metals in sediments tended to escalate in fine-grained sediments. The region experiences prolonged waterlogging throughout much of the year, resulting in low groundwater flushing rates. Consequently, observed variations in mean arsenic concentrations during the monsoon season differed from those in the pre-monsoon season, as detailed in Table 1.2. Sampling sites in Ghazipur district included Bhavarkole, Reotipur, and Karanda blocks.

Table 1.2 Distribution of Arsenic during Post monsoon& Pre monsoon in Blocks of Ghazipur district

Blocks in Ghazipur district	As in ppb	
	Post monsoon	Pre monsoon
Bhavarkole	15	22
Reotipur	17	27
Karanda	45	52

In the Ganga–Meghna–Brahmaputra region, approximately 3000 communities exhibit arsenic concentrations surpassing 50 parts per million (ppm), posing a significant threat to the well-being of approximately 6 million individuals. Prolonged exposure to arsenic leads to severe health consequences, including skin lesions, premature hair depigmentation, accelerated aging, and the development of cancer.

It has been observed that in West Bengal, India, sedimentary soil comprises pyrite, magnetite, hematite, quartz, and calcite minerals, releasing arsenic through mineral dissolution mechanisms. Bihar’s fluvial geomorphology may influence arsenic dissemination, resulting in lower levels of SO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ and a limited association with arsenic. Pre-Cenozoic metamorphics and Riverian alluvial deposits release arsenic into the groundwater of Jharkhand, a process further intensified in the presence of organic carbon [21,22].

Each sample shows variation in arsenic (As) concentrations due to seasonal variation. There is a decrease in arsenic concentration from the pre-monsoon to post-monsoon season. The cause of variation is the change in groundwater level during the rainy season and also the consumption of groundwater in the irrigation process. Arsenic concentration fluctuation during pre and post-monsoon seasons is correlated in terms of its concentration. A direct relationship exists between arsenic concentration and the average amount of rainfall in the rainy season. Arsenic concentration decreases with an increase in the amount of rainfall as it increases the rate of dilution of arsenic in water.

To address arsenic contamination in India’s groundwater, active community involvement is crucial. Arsenic mobility and removal factors pose challenges, and various removal technologies are assessed for efficacy, affordability, and scalability. Non-governmental organizations employ sustainable techniques, including affordable household filters. Community water purifiers and arsenic removal plants have successfully reduced arsenic concentrations by up to 90%. Additionally, rainwater collection contributes to improving water quality. The significant health risks associated with arsenic exposure underscore the urgency of comprehensively addressing this issue. Strategies and interventions must be tailored to the unique challenges and geological conditions of each affected area [23,24,25].

The study recommends establishing a regular national monitoring system using GIS to identify arsenic hotspots. Collaborative efforts involving policymakers, researchers, and local communities are deemed essential to mitigate the adverse effects of arsenic contamination and ensure access to safe drinking water for affected populations.

FUTURE SCOPE

- **Advanced Monitoring and Mapping:** Implementing advanced monitoring techniques, such as remote sensing and GIS-based mapping, to continuously monitor arsenic levels and identify hotspots. This will enable early detection of contamination and facilitate targeted intervention strategies.
- **Understanding Biogeochemical Processes:** Furthering our understanding of the complex biogeochemical processes that control arsenic mobilization and transformation in groundwater systems. This includes studying microbial interactions, redox reactions, and mineral-water interactions that influence arsenic behavior.
- **Development of Innovative Remediation Technologies:** Investing in research and development of innovative arsenic removal technologies that are cost-effective, scalable, and suitable for diverse geological settings. This may include decentralized treatment systems, biofiltration methods, and hybrid approaches combining physical, chemical, and biological processes.
- **Community Engagement and Capacity Building:** Strengthening community engagement and capacity building initiatives to raise awareness about arsenic contamination, its health impacts, and available mitigation strategies. Empowering local communities to participate in monitoring, decision-making, and implementation of interventions is essential for long-term sustainability.
- **Policy and Governance:** Advocating for robust policy frameworks and governance mechanisms to regulate arsenic levels in drinking water and promote sustainable management of groundwater resources. This involves collaboration between governments, research institutions, NGOs, and international agencies to prioritize safe drinking water access.
- **Health Impact Studies:** Conducting comprehensive health impact studies to assess the long-term health effects of arsenic exposure on affected populations. This includes epidemiological research, biomonitoring studies, and health risk assessments to inform public health interventions and medical care.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** Considering the implications of climate change on arsenic contamination and groundwater dynamics. Climate variability, such as changing precipitation patterns and sea-level rise, may influence groundwater recharge rates and arsenic mobility, necessitating adaptive strategies.

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